

Conference Abstract

The role of academic mentoring in empowering new-generation scientists for a sustainable future

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Abstract

In an era of unprecedented global challenges and declining public trust in scientific institutions (Tyson and Kennedy 2024), academic mentoring has become essential in preparing new generation scientists to navigate complex, interdisciplinary fields and effect meaningful societal change. By fostering collaboration across various disciplines and sectors, academic mentoring equips early-stage researchers to engage effectively with policymakers, industry leaders, and civil society. This collaborative approach is crucial for addressing pressing environmental and social issues, such as climate change and biodiversity loss. Effective mentoring not only enhances scientific expertise but also builds leadership, communication, and engagement skills, thereby bridging the gap between research and its societal impact (Taddicken and Krämer 2021).

Mentorship is especially vital for women in science, as research suggests that women are often less likely to self-promote and take leadership roles, despite equal or superior qualifications compared to their male counterparts (Ertl et al. 2017). Women frequently face implicit biases, structural barriers, and a lack of role models, which can hinder their academic advancement (Shen 2013). Structured mentoring programs have been shown to improve confidence, networking, and career progression for women in STEM fields (Amon 2017, Lantz-Deaton et al. 2018).

Furthermore, mentoring serves as a bridge between students and professors, fostering mutual understanding and effective communication. This is particularly important as many countries are experiencing a decline in higher education enrollment. For instance,

recent data indicates a significant drop in college enrollment in the United States, with a 5% decrease in 18-year-old freshmen for the fall semester (Shapiro 2024). Factors contributing to this trend include not only the rising tuition costs and demographic shifts (Witkowski 2016), but also concerns about the value of a college degree and fear of study-related stress (survey by Collage Rover, January 2025). By implementing effective mentoring programs, universities can enhance student engagement and retention, addressing some of these challenges (Pleschová and McAlpine 2015). To address this issue, mentoring techniques should be taught to all academics who work with students. Universities should invest in mentoring hubs to strengthen the connection between students and faculty, thereby preparing well-rounded graduates for the professional world and their role as young adults entering society. A systematic review of mentoring in higher education highlights the positive impact of such programs on student career development, emphasizing the need for structured mentoring initiatives within academic institutions (Nabi et al. 2024).

At the same time, concerns about the well-being of academics themselves are growing (Bamforth et al. 2024), citing reasons such as a performance-based culture, increasing pressure to generate research income, publish in prestigious journals, excessive workload, work intensification, and work-family conflict (Turner and Garvis 2023). Academic staff are reporting high levels of stress and burnout (Simons et al. 2019, Kinman and Johnson 2019), and university-level risk management has the opportunity to support academics in adopting well-being and coping behaviors (Bamforth et al. 2024). Therefore, universities' investments in multilayered mentoring appear urgently needed.

Academic mentoring is currently undergoing a strong transformation, with social media emerging as a powerful tool for academic support, networking, and outreach. Platforms such as LinkedIn and ResearchGate, facilitate knowledge exchange and global collaborations, allowing early-career researchers to engage beyond traditional institutional boundaries (Ali et al. 2022, Deeken et al. 2020). Moreover, social media plays a crucial role in science education, making complex topics more accessible and engaging to the public. However, it also presents challenges, including misinformation, online harassment, and the risk of oversimplifying scientific discourse (Taddicken and Krämer 2021).

Finally, science communication remains a cornerstone of public trust in science (Szabados 2019). The rise of misinformation and skepticism toward scientific institutions and science as such (West and Bergstrom 2021, Treen et al. 2020) underscores the urgency of equipping scientists with the skills to effectively communicate their findings. Mentoring can empower researchers to engage with the public, counter misinformation, and advocate for evidence-based policies. Effective science communication is not only essential for raising awareness on climate change but also for addressing the broader scientific credibility crisis (Lewandowsky 2021). As we navigate these pressing global issues, fostering a new generation of engaged, transdisciplinary scientists through mentoring is paramount for creating a resilient and sustainable future.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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